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**International Research Conference on Business,
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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2023**'s main theme is "***New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities***". In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2023** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

ABOUT 7 MISTAKES THAT OUR WOMEN AND GIRLS MAKE IN LOSING WEIGHT

Sobira TURSUNBOYEVA

*Nutritionist, Head of the "Healthy Slimming Center"
Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

1. Attempting to lose weight without knowing the cause of obesity.

Pay attention to the types of obesity. If obesity is caused by improper diet, the weight will not exceed 10 kg. If obesity is the result of hormonal disorders, the excess weight will be more than 10 kg.

2. Improper nutrition is the main cause of malnutrition frequent starvation in women with abdominal circumference of more than 80 cm, in men - more than 90 cm.

3. Deficiency can currently only be caused by vitamin D deficiency and overweight. An additional example would be magnesium deficiency.

In vitamin D deficiency, there is also rapid opening of the abdomen, frequent sweating and low energy. On the other hand, magnesium deficient women often experience headaches, premature dieting, and inability to exercise for long periods of time.

4. Insulin resistance. Unfortunately, many women-our daughters-have insulin resistance. And these women, as a result of snacking 5 times a day, torture themselves with poor nutrition.

Insulin resistance is a condition in which cells lose sensitivity to insulin and do not pass glucose inside. As a result, organs and tissues do not receive the necessary energy, and blood sugar levels rise. A metabolic disorder develops.

5. Consumption of food inappropriate to human nature, expectoration of phlegm by a female client and drinking large quantities of water.

6. Going on a protein diet, completely eliminating fats and carbohydrates from your diet, is also a big mistake.

7. Lack of sleep in moderation and sedentary lifestyle without daily exercise. Diet + sport is definitely necessary to expend the calories consumed while exercising.

And at night from 22:00 to 03:00 it is necessary to sleep at the time when melatonin harmonic is produced!

Dear women, if you want to lose weight, do not repeat mistakes when eating on your own!

If you have had cases of increased appetite, weakness, be sure to see a nutrino-logist, and now get examined by a Endocrinologist!

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